

Assessment on Organization and Management of Secondary Schools in Oyo Metropolis using Information and Communication Technology Device

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Abstract

The study investigated the assessment on organization and management of secondary schools in Oyo metropolis using information and communication technology device. The study adopted a descriptive survey design. The population consisted of all the 1570 secondary schools in Oyo metropolis during the 2022/2023 academic session. Sample of 539 coeducational secondary schools were randomly selected from the target population. The research instrument used for the study was questionnaire titled 'School Organization and Management Using ICT Device Questionnaire [SOAMUICTDQ]'. The instrument was validated by the experts in information and communication technology and educational management and the reliability coefficient of 0.80 was obtained using Cronbach alpha reliability test. The generated data were analyzed using regressions and chi-square. The results from the analysis revealed that information and communication technology had significant influence on school organization and management in Oyo Metropolis. It also played significant roles in school documentation and enhanced the stability of the organization of school management in Oyo metropolis. The study concluded that school administrators' functions such as record keeping, document processing and organizing can be made more effective and efficient through the application of information and communication technology devices. The study recommended that government should make provision for information and communication technology facilities in schools so as to put an end to exposition of school documents that are confidential to the public.

Keywords: Information and Communication Technology, Documentation, Organization and Management.

Introduction

The management, governance and administration of school require proper organization and documentation of schools records, activities and projects. Therefore, school administrators are saddled with the responsibility of proper management of the activities and provide instructional leadership in school. The functions of the school administrators include record keeping, document processing, reporting, planning, organizing, knowledge management, communication and decision making. Umeri (2022) reported that records play a strategic role in the effective and efficient administration of the school. The records of the teaching process restore competence and preserve the trends in the school. Therefore, data preservation is crucial because it helps the school meet its own learning objectives, which include equipping students with skills for postsecondary education and making them useful members of society.

Science and technology have become a power engine under which every nation across the globe tap their energy source (Nchunge, David, Maurice, & Waweru 2013). As the world changes, information and knowledge changes rapidly, teaching and learning processes as well as the management of schools also have to change. The implementation of cutting-edge

technology in the classroom is linked to adjustments in both teaching and learning processes as well as the way administrative duties are handled in schools. The process of organization and documentation in school can only be effective in the place where information and communication technology has been put in operation (Ajayi, & Haastrup, 2011). Opati (2013) defined information and communication technology as a medium through which information is retrieved, use and stored as a data base. Information and Communication Technology (ICT) provides medium for interaction, assimilate, and collaborate, documentation, organization and control in educational circle (Meleisea, 2007). Rana (2019) asserted that ICT holds the key to the success of modernizing information services. While there are many uses for ICT, its primary application is in digitizing the current paper-based records for storage, retrieval, and distribution. Atakpa, Amah and Obi (2022) reported that with the help of information and communication technology (ICT), users now use various types of technologies to aid the retrieval of documents and information. One way that ICT development is changing how people access, retrieve, store, alter, and transmit information is in the fields of computing, communication, and mass storage technologies.

Federal Ministry of Education had seen the important of science and technology and they had deem it fit to create ICT department and also collaborate with several government agencies and other stakeholders in the private sector to employ ICT driven projects in Nigeria (Osakwe, 2012). The conventional ways of keeping records in the schools had paralyzed our educational sector. It is time for our educational sector to bring in an innovation that will make it withstand expected changes and development that are trending round the world. Carless (2013) saw ICT as innovation that all educational sectors can employ to bring improvement or changes on the way of doing things to achieve particular set goals.

Godwin (2021) stressed that system of organization and management in the past suffer a setback especially when such information wants to be retrieved. Today, many schools in Nigeria are faced with challenges of how to use Information Communication Technology (ICT) devices to organize and to document their records. The documents that are supposed to be saved or kept in a data base were kept in a file and put in a wall dope for termites and rats to consume. Schools in the present existence require administrators and leaders to ensure that Performance of job duties takes place in an operative manner with the use of technologies that are suitable to their needs and requirements. Teachers, administrators, and other support personnel can simplify their daily tasks and maintain track of everything that occurs in the office, classroom, and other locations with the use of school records documentation and management software (Umeri, 2022). Science and technology help schools management enhance information dissemination, adequate updating and enlightenment (Wedell, 2009). Information explosion, computer hardware and software, telecommunications, and digital electronics speed up the volume of the work done in an organization. Osakwe (2012) emphasized the use of ICT in our institution of learning starting from university education to primary and secondary schools sectors. Effective learning outcome can be achieved when our mode of instruction and techniques have technological basis rather conventional techniques (Balanskat, Blainire&Kefala, 2006). Nigeria secondary schools lack ICT facilities to run school activities. The confidential documents of schools were always exposed to outsider simply because commercial cyber cafés help them in the documentation of vital documents. In the light of this, study examined the assessment on organization and management of secondary schools in Oyo metropolis using information and communication technology device

Today, science and technology devices (STD) are very important in the learning and teaching process at all levels of education. However, in Nigeria, the use of ICT is still in its infancy. Majority of our secondary schools in Nigeria lack proper documentation, on how the schools are running (Wedell, 2009). They are not efficient in the organisation of school records, enrolments and school planning simply because they are not in a digital circle (Wedell, 2009). There is a gap between the school administrators, teachers and students because ICT that supposed to link them to global world are not put in place (Osakwe, 2012). Not only this, where the ICT are being used, there is no enough fund to maintain the gadgets, no experts to operate them and also no regular electricity supply for its operation (Osakwe, 2012). Therefore, this study was carried out to investigate the assessment on organization and management of secondary schools in Oyo metropolis using information and communication technology device.

Objectives of the Study

The aim of this study was to investigate the assessment on organization and management of secondary schools in Oyo metropolis using information and communication technology device

. Specifically, the objectives study sought to:

1. Examine the influence of information and communication technology on school management in Oyo metropolis.
2. investigate the importance of information and communication technology on secondary school documentation in Oyo metropolis

3. Examine how information and communication technology influence the documentation of secondary school in Oyo metropolis.

Research Questions

1. What is the influence of information and communication technology on secondary school management in Oyo Metropolis?
2. What is the importance of information and communication technology on secondary school documentation in Oyo metropolis?
3. How does information and communication technology stabilize the organization and management of secondary schools in Oyo Metropolis?

Hypothesis

H0₁: There is no significant influence of information and communication technology on documentation in the school management in Oyo metropolis

H0₂: There is no significant influence of information and communication technology on organization in the school management in Oyo metropolis

Methodology

The study adopted a descriptive survey design. The population consisted of all 1570 secondary schools in Oyo metropolis. A sample of coeducational secondary schools was purposively selected for the study. The research instrument used for the study was questionnaire 'titled School Organization and Management Using ICT Device Questionnaire (SOAMUICTDQ). The face and content of the instrument was validated by the experts in information and communication technology and educational management. The reliability coefficient of 0.80 was obtained using Cronbach alpha reliability test. The generated data were analyzed using simple regressions and chi-square at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Research Question 1: What is the influence of information and communication technology on secondary school management in Oyo Metropolis?

Table 1: Summary of Simple Regression Analysis of Influence of Information and communication Technology on School Management in Oyo Metropolis

R	R. Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate		
.618 ^a	.383	.376	.32331		
Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean	F	Sig
Regression	735410.42	1	735410.42	1575.932	.002
Residual	251525.00	539		466.651	
Total	986935.42	538			

Source: *Fieldwork, 2023*

Table 1 revealed the influence of information and communication technology on school management in Oyo metropolis. The table show a coefficient of simple correlation (R = .618 and a multiple R²of .383). This means that 38% of the total variance observed in the study while 62% of the variance was accounted for by the variables not considered in the study. Also the F ratio of 1575.932 from the analysis of variance shows that the simple regression is statistically significant.

Research Question 2: What is the importance of information and communication technology on secondary school documentation in Oyo metropolis?

Table 2: Summary of Simple Regression Analysis of Importance of Information and Communication Technology on School Documentation in Oyo Metropolis

R	R. Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate		
.258 ^a	.066	.057	.3974		
Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig
Regression	3196.4581	1	3196.4581	62.290	.000
Residual	25603.786	539	47.5023		
Total	28800.2441	538			

Source: *Fieldwork, 2023*

Table 2 showed the importance of science and technology on school documentation. The table show a coefficient of multiple correlation (R = .258). The table also shows that science and technology significantly enhanced efficient organization and documentation in school management and accounted for 6.6% of the total variance observed in the study. The F ratio 62.290 from the analysis of variance shows that the regression is significant

Research Question 3: How does information and communication technology stabilize the organization and management of secondary schools in Oyo Metropolis?

Table 3: Summary of Simple Regression Analysis of Influence of Information and Communication Technology on Stabilization of School Management in Oyo Metropolis

R	R. Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate		
.428 ^a	.085	.301	.342		
Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig
Regression	40454.486	1	40454.486	367.107	.001
Residual	59397.234	539	110.198		
Total	99851.72	538			

Source: *Fieldwork, 2023*

Table 3 showed how science and technology stabilized the school management. 8.5% of the variance observed. The F ratio of 367.107 from the analysis of variance shows that the regression is statistically significant

H₀₁: There is no significant influence of information and communication technology on documentation in the school management in Oyo metropolis

Table 4: Analysis of Chi- Square Showing Influence of Information and Communication Technology on School Documentation Oyo Metropolis

Value	Df	Asymp. Sig.	(2-sided)	
Pearson Chi-Square	27.395 ^a	1	.0246	
Likelihood Ratio	27.252	539	.428	
Linear-by-Linear Association	27.341	538	.394	

N of valid Cases 500

A cell (66.7%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 54. 21. Since the Asymptotic significant 2-sided value (.0246) is less than alpha value .05, the null hypothesis is therefore rejected meaning that there is significant influence of information and communication technology on organization in the school Management in Oyo Metropolis

H₀₂: There is no significant influence of information and communication technology on organization in the school management in Oyo metropolis

Table 4: Analysis of Chi- Square Showing Influence of Information and Communication Technology on School Management in Oyo Metropolis

Value	Df	Asymp. Sig.	(2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	265.784 ^a	1	.041
Likelihood Ratio	364.267	539	.740
Linear-by-Linear Association	0.014	538	.523
N of Valid Cases	500		

a. 0 cells (33.3%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 54. 21. Since the Asymptotic significant 2-sided value (.041) is less than alpha value .05, the null hypothesis is therefore rejected meaning that there is no significant influence of science information and communication technology on documentation in the school management in Oyo Metropolis

Discussion of findings

The study assessed the organization and management of secondary schools in Oyo metropolis using information and communication technology device. The major findings of the study revealed that information and communication technology enhanced effective organization and documentation in school management. Information and communication technology had significant influence on school management in Oyo Metropolis. It also played significant roles in school documentation and enhanced the stability of the organization of school management in Oyo Metropolis. Majority of respondents agreed that the day to day functions of the school administrators which include record keeping, document processing, reporting, planning, organizing, knowledge management, communication and decision making were made more effective and efficient through the application of information and communication technology. This result supported the findings of Umeri (2022), who stated that school record documentation and management software facilitates the organization of everyday tasks and aids teachers, administrators, and other support staff members in keeping tabs on events that occur in the office, classroom, and other locations. Atakpa, Amah and Obi (2022) indicated in their findings that with the help of information and communication technology (ICT), users now use various types of technologies to aid the retrieval of documents and information. One area where ICT progress is changing how people access, retrieve, store, manipulate, and distribute information is mass storage technologies. Carless (2013) also stated that ICT create a medium at which documents can be kept and retrieved when needed. Wedell, (2009) buttressed this findings with the statement that ICT speed up the volume of the work done in an organization.

Conclusion

It can be concluded from the result of the study that information and communication technology had significant influence on school organization and management in Oyo Metropolis. It also played significant roles in school documentation and enhanced the stability of the organization of school management in Oyo Metropolis. The day to day functions of the school administrators which include record keeping, document processing, reporting, planning, organizing, knowledge management, communication and decision making were made more effective and efficient through the application of science and technology.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made:

1. Information and Communication Technology should be employed in school management at all level of education.

2. Government must make provision for Information and Communication Technology facilities in schools so as to put an end to exposition of school documents that are confidential to the public.
3. Enabling environment must be created for teachers and school administrators to undergo training on how to use Information and Communication Technology facilities while discharging their duties.

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